

COMPUTER AIDED DESIGN FOR COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

A new approach for computer aided design of composite structure is proposed. This approach pays attention to the three-dimensional stresses and strains, particularly the interlaminar stresses and strains.

A package for the analysis of composite beam has been developed and presented. This COMPBEAM package utilizes three-dimensional finite elements and gives interlaminar stresses.

Beams with different boundary and loading conditions can be analyzed. The finite element mesh is fixed. The program is designed to run on a microcomputer. This computer aided design package allows designers and researchers to have a quick picture of the complete stress and strain distribution in laminated composite beams.

INTRODUCTION

Structures made up of high performance composite materials are usually of laminated form. Stress analysis for the design of these structures is therefore tedious and complicated. A simple determination of components of modulus such as A_{ij} , B_{ij} and D_{ij} for a laminate containing more than two layers already requires considerable time and effort. Apart from educational purposes, hand calculations are certainly not recommended, not only because of the time and effort involved, but also because there are many sources of calculation error. Besides, the rapid development of microcomputers has increased the computing power available to the scientist and engineer tremendously. Furthermore, the rate of development is more likely to accelerate rather than slow down in the near future. With this trend it is inevitable that more thorough and complete analysis routines will be developed to replace earlier methods which are based on simple laminate theory. The computationally expensive but more accurate finite element technique is poised to exploit the recent advances in computer processing ability.

Over the past four years, activities on computer aided design for composites have increased rapidly. The following shows a brief summary of these programs. All programs run on microcomputers.

Many programs have been developed at the University of Delaware. These programs use laminate theory. One example is a program called COMPCAL (1984) [1]. The COMPCAL program combines micromechanics and lamination theory. It can be used to calculate lamina elastic constants, thermal expansion coefficients, transport properties and similar properties for laminates. The program determines ply stress and strain which is then evaluated with respect to the quadratic failure criterion.

THINK COMPOSITES software club [2] has a few programs. The MICMAC program uses spreadsheets that are specialized for plates, pressure vessels, tubing, beams, etc. RANK is a program that rates given laminates performance for specified design constraints. There are also programs for stress analysis and design such as LAMINATE, DESIGN and FEMBEAM.

FCI Management Services Inc. [3] released a program called SUPERLAM in 1986. This program also uses micromechanics, laminate theory and the quadratic failure criterion. The program is capable of predicting elastic properties, as well as stresses and strains due to applied loads, displacements, temperature changes and moisture effects. Laminated composites and filament wound products are considered. In essence, this program is not much different from other programs mentioned above except that it emphasizes unsymmetrical laminates and has a different mode of user operation. It is geared toward designing pressure vessels in the chemical processing industry.

HYBRID, a program designed at Concordia University [4] also uses laminate theory for plates and cylinders. The difference between this program and the others previously mentioned is that graphical representation of stress and strain variation in the laminate can be obtained. Quadratic failure criterion is also used but the strain vector is calculated in three-dimensional strain space ($\epsilon_1, \epsilon_2, \epsilon_6$) [5].

The above programs focus on analysis of structural elements such as plates or cylinders. Currently there are efforts to provide computer aided design for a whole structure. COCOMAT [6] developers intended to provide a computer aided engineering system for information management, geometry handling, and analysis support in the preliminary design of aircraft structures. The CADFIBER [7] program package has for its aim the development of a total concept for computer aided design and production of fiber composite materials. This package is intended to be comprehensive and has many modules which include material data base, construction and dimensioning, process simulation, production and quality assurance.

Past and current efforts on computer aided design of composites have only dealt with the elementary or the global aspects of the topic. Programs dealing with structural elements such as plates or cylinders use laminate theory, therefore only in-plane stress and strain can be obtained. It is well understood that in composite structures, interlaminar stresses play an important role in structural failure. To the author's knowledge, at the present time, there is no computer aided design package available that can provide interlaminar stresses and strains in

composite structures. To obtain interlaminar stress requires utilization of numerical techniques such as three-dimensional finite elements. There are many commercial finite element programs available such as ANSYS [8], NASTRAN [9] and NISA [10]. These are large and versatile programs that have features of stress analysis, vibration, buckling, etc. Due to their large size, users of these programs need to be well trained. To use these programs to analyze a composite structure requires further knowledge on fiber orientation, generation of meshes as well as the post treatment of results.

At the present time, advanced composites are used mainly in the aircraft industry where the structure is mainly of the form of plates and shells and aircraft companies usually have personnel specially assigned to deal with composites. As such programs such as ANSYS, NASTRAN and NISA would be adequate. However, if composites were to be expanded into the industrial applications where structural forms very often have the shape of beams, rods, columns, cylinders, etc. and where there may not be sufficient personnel who is specialized in finite element and composite structure, then specialized programs that can do finite element analysis on composite structural elements would speed up the expansion. To ensure general accessibility and portability, microcomputers should be chosen to carry out the calculations. At the outset, microcomputers may seem to be too small and too slow. However, except for large companies and where large computers are easily accessible, small companies usually do not have access to adequate facilities. Even if they do, time sharing is required and waiting time for the large computers can easily eliminate the computational advantage of the larger computer. Additionally, microcomputers are increasing their processor speeds. Machines such as Compaq 386/25 can run as fast as many mini computers. It is with the above reasons that the project of computer aided design for composite structures at Concordia University was initiated. The aim of the project is to provide three-dimensional stress and strains in structural elements such as beams, plates and shells subjected to various loads and boundary conditions. Many modular programs using three-dimensional finite elements are developed. These programs are designed to run on microcomputers. This paper presents one of the programs, COMPBEAM, which is particularly designed for beam analysis.

COMPBEAM [11]

COMPBEAM program uses a three-dimensional 20 node orthotropic finite element [12]. The program can analyze beams with up to 25 layers. Each layer is modelled with 72 finite elements. Four types of beams can be analyzed (Figure 1). They are non-symmetric / non-cantilever, symmetric / non-cantilever, non-symmetric / cantilever and symmetric / cantilever. The symmetry line refers to the support and loading conditions rather than the lay up arrangement which can be unsymmetric. The boundary conditions can be either clamped, simply supported or free. A data base is provided for different materials. Loads can be distributed or concentrated. Graphical representation of the stated problem as well as the display of the results is available. The results displayed can be in the form of a deformation plot, variation of stress components ($\sigma_x, \sigma_y, \sigma_z, \sigma_{xy}, \sigma_{yz}, \sigma_{xz}$), strain components ($\epsilon_x, \epsilon_y, \epsilon_z, \epsilon_{xy}, \epsilon_{yz}, \epsilon_{xz}$) or structural displacement along any direction (x, y or z).

Since the program is designed to run on microcomputers, a special algorithm which utilizes submatrix manipulation has been used. This technique uses submatrices as single pieces of information. Using this technique reduces the number of times required to read and write on the disk storage media, thus speeds up the execution time [13].

VERIFICATION EXAMPLE

In order to verify the accuracy of the program, interlaminar stresses in a beam subjected to bending loads are calculated. The elasticity solution was obtained by Pagano [14]. Figure 2 shows the configuration of the beam under investigation. Details of the problem are:

- Stacking of the beam [0/90/0]
- Material properties (high modulus graphite/epoxy)

$$\begin{aligned}
 E_L &= 171 \text{ GPa (25 msi)} \\
 E_T &= 6.83 \text{ GPa (1 msi)} \\
 G_{LT} &= 3.42 \text{ GPa (0.50 msi)} \\
 G_{TT} &= 1.37 \text{ GPa (0.2 msi)} \\
 \nu_{TT} &= \nu_{LT} = 0.25
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

where L = direction parallel to the fibers
 T = direction transverse to the fibers
 ν_{LT} = Poisson ratio measuring strain in the transverse direction under uniaxial normal stress in the L direction.

- Loading condition $q(x) = q_0 \sin \frac{\pi x}{l}$ (2)

- Boundary conditions:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \sigma_z(x, h/2) &= q(x) \\
 \sigma_z(x, -h/2) &= \sigma_{xz}(x, \pm h/2) = 0 \\
 \sigma_x(0, z) &= \sigma_x(l, z) = 0 \\
 w(0, z) &= w(l, z) = 0
 \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

- Length to thickness ratio $l/h = 4$

Pagano [14] analyzed the plate as a plane strain problem. Continuity of displacement and traction at the interfaces was satisfied. Pagano results were shown for $\bar{\sigma}_z = \frac{\sigma_z(l/2, z)}{q_0}$ and

$\bar{\sigma}_{xz} = \frac{\sigma_{xz}(0, z)}{q_0}$ for both the classical plate theory solution and for the elasticity solution. These results are shown in Figures 3 and 4. ($\bar{z} = \frac{z}{h}$)

COMPBEAM SOLUTION

Using COMPBEAM, after the input of the problem has been entered, the input can be verified as shown in Figure 5. Input information only consists of:

- Beam geometry (length, width, number of layers)
- Layer information (fiber orientation, material type, layer thickness and stacking sequence)
- Loading location and values
- Support locations

For better accuracy, the lay up of the beam is $[0_2/90_2/0_2]$ where the thickness of each layer is half of a regular lamina thickness. The beam is modelled as symmetric / non-cantilever and therefore only half length of the beam is modelled. There are 36 uniform elements in this half length, two elements in the half width and one element per layer making a total of 432 three-dimensional elements. The boundary conditions are modelled as:

At face $x = 0$ $w = 0$ (w is displacement along z direction) (4)

At face $x = \ell/2$ $u = 0$ (u is displacement along x direction) (5)

At face $y = w/2$ $v = 0$ (v is displacement along y direction) (6)

Boundary condition (4) is to be the same as boundary condition (3) in Pagano solution [14]. Boundary conditions (5) and (6) are based on symmetry.

The loading condition as used in equation (2) is discretized over each element. There are 36 uniform elements over a length of $\ell/2$, and the length of each element along the x direction is $\frac{\ell}{72}$. Value of $q(x)$ at the middle of each element is calculated. For example:

- For the first element on the left hand side $q = q_0 \sin \frac{\pi}{144}$
- For the second element from the left hand side $q = q_0 \sin \frac{3\pi}{144}$ and so on.

These values are entered as total loads acting at the center of each element. The preprocessing package converts these loads into uniform pressure acting over the face of each element. These uniform pressures are calculated as

$$p = \frac{N}{w\ell_0} \quad (7)$$

where

- p = uniform pressure
- N = load as entered
- w = total width of the beam
- ℓ_0 = length of each element (for the symmetric case, it is equal to $\frac{\ell}{72}$ where ℓ is beam length)

The finite element program then discretizes the uniform pressures into nodal loads following normal virtual work procedure.

Actual dimensions of the beam are:

$$h = 0.76 \text{ mm}, w = 1.52 \text{ mm}, l = 3.04 \text{ mm}$$

These give an aspect ratio of $l/h = 4$.

The solution took three hours on a COMPAQ 386-20 microcomputer. Some of the results obtained are shown in Figures 6, 7 for σ_{xz} and σ_z variation across the thickness and length. These are compared with Pagano's results as shown in Figure 3 and 4.

The finite element stresses were calculated at the gauss points within the element. Nodal stresses were extrapolated from these gaussian values. Curves shown in Figure 6, 7 were constructed using stress values at the mid node of each side of the element.

The finite element results show reasonable agreement with the elasticity solution by Pagano [14].

CONCLUSION

A computer aided design package that can accurately calculate three-dimensional stresses in laminated composite beam has been developed and proven. The program can be run on a microcomputer and can handle most relevant problems within a reasonable time.

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FIGURE 1(b) : non-symmetric

FIGURE 1(A) : symmetric option

FIGURE 1(c) double cantilever symmetric

FIGURE 1(d) : left cantilever

FIGURE 2 : Simply supported beam under loading condition

FIGURE 3 : Variation of $\bar{\sigma}_{xz}$ over the thickness of the laminate at $x = 0$

FIGURE 4: Variation of $\bar{\sigma}_z$ over the laminate thickness at $x = 1/2$

Figure 5: Verification of input for [0/90/0] beam

Figure 6: Shear stress σ_{xz} distribution across thickness at $x = 0$ (Pagano beam)

Figure 7: Normal stress σ_z distribution across thickness at $1/2$ (Pagano beam)